

New Stability Analysis for Neural Networks with Time-Varying Delays

Authors : Miaomiao Yang, Shouming Zhong

Abstract : This paper studies the problem of globally asymptotic stability analysis for neural networks with time-varying delay. By establishing a suitable Lyapunov-Krasovskii function, and several novel sufficient conditions is obtained to guarantee the asymptotically stability of the considered system. Finally, it can be demonstrated by numerical examples that our derived results reduce the conservatism more efficiently than some present results.

Keywords : Neural networks, Lyapunov-Krasovskii, Time-varying delay, Linear matrix inequality,

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014